

MEASUREMENT OF THE RESIDUAL MOISTURE CONTENT OF THE MATERIAL DURING ROLLER COMPACTION

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Abstract. The study is devoted to the analytical description of the residual moisture content of the material during roller pressing. It was found that the amount of fluid extracted at the beginning of the compression zone grows faster, then, the growth rate decreases, and at the end of the compression zone, the amount of extracted fluid stabilizes. It was established that the patterns of change in the extracted fluid in the restoration zone depend on the angle that determines the position of the point where the fluid changes direction.

Keywords: roller squeezing, moisture filtration, residual moisture, squeezing area.

Introduction

The theoretical description of the roll squeezing process is one of the most difficult tasks of modern mechanics, since it is necessary to jointly solve the contact and hydraulic problems in a two-roll module.

In works [1-8], contact problems of roll squeezing were solved, and in works [9-20], hydraulic problems were solved.

When studying the roll squeezing process of any materials, one of the main tasks is to determine the analytical dependence of the residual moisture on the parameters of the roll pressing.

The main task of the roller pressing process is to provide the residual moisture content of the pressed material required by the technological process. Therefore, when studying the process of roll squeezing of any materials, one of the main problems is to determine the analytical dependence of the residual moisture on the parameters of the roll pressing process.

In the theory of roll pressing of wet materials, research on modeling the residual moisture of the pressed material is conducted in three directions.

The first direction is experimental, based on experimental data, using the methods of mathematical statistics and experiment planning, obtained in the form of empirical or regression dependencies [10,15,19].

The second direction is experimental-theoretical, built by theoretical research on the basis of empirical dependencies experimentally obtained [14,17,18].

The third direction is theoretical, based on the theoretical study of hydraulic phenomena occurring in the contact zone of the rolls with the pressed material [12,13,14,19].

An analysis of the literature sources showed that the models of residual moisture obtained by experimental methods are mainly used for their intended purpose. The degree of further application of the residual moisture formula obtained by the experimental-theoretical method depends on the empirical dependencies used in it. A correct model of residual moisture obtained by theoretical methods is not currently available. The models available at present can be used in studies of particular cases of roll pressing.

In [20], analytical dependencies were determined that describe the residual moisture content of the pressed material for a symmetrical two-roll module. In order to further develop theoretical concepts, given in [2,7], the object of study is a generalized two-roll module, in which the rolls are located relative to the vertical line at an angle of β to the right, have unequal diameters ($D_1 \neq D_2$) with elastic coatings, a layer of fibrous (processed) material has a uniform thickness and is fed tilted down relative to the line of centers at an angle of γ_1 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Scheme of a two-roll module
 of squeezing machine

Materials and methods

The lower roll contact curve (curve A_1A_2) consists of two zones A_1A_3 and A_3A_2 . In zone A_1A_3 , the fibrous material and the roll coating are compressed, and in A_3A_2 the strain is restored.

Let us first consider the process of fluid filtration in zone A_1A_3 .

In the compression zone for the two-roll module under consideration, we have [2]:

$$r_{11} = \frac{R_1}{1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11}} \left(1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11} \frac{\cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)}{\cos(\theta_{11} + \gamma)} \right), \quad -(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1) \leq \theta_{11} + \gamma \leq 0, \quad (1)$$

$$r'_{11} = \frac{k_{11}\lambda_{11}R_1}{1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11}} \cos \varphi_{11} \frac{\sin \theta_{11}}{\cos^2 \theta_{11}}. \quad (2)$$

где $k_{11} = \frac{m_{11}H_1 \sin(\varphi_{11} + \varphi_{21})}{m_1^* \delta_1 \sin(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)}$, $\lambda_{11} = \frac{A_{11}^* m_{11}^* (\Delta l_{11})_{cp} - (A_{11}(1 - m_{11}) - A_{11}^*(1 - m_{11}^*)) h_{11}^0}{A_{11} m_{11} (\Delta l_{11})_{cp} + (A_{11}(1 - m_{11}) - A_{11}^*(1 - m_{11}^*)) H_1}$;

$$h_{11}^0 = \delta_1 \frac{\sin(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)}{\sin(\varphi_{11} + \varphi_{21})}; \quad (\Delta l_{11})_{cp} = R_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\sin 2(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)}{2(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)} \right),$$

here m_{11} – is the coefficient of strengthening of the points of the elastic coating of the lower roll under compression, m_1^* – is the coefficient of strengthening of the points of the processed material under compression.

As is known from [9], the amount of removed fluid flowing along the roll contact curve can be determined by the following expression

$$dG = B\rho u_\theta dh, \tag{3}$$

where B – is the width of the wet material; ρ – is the fluid density; u_θ – is the filtration rate in direction θ .

In the compression zone A_1A_3 , the filtration rate $u_{11\theta}$ is described by the following formula [12]:

$$u_{11\theta} = -b_{11}((\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^3 + (\theta_{11} + \gamma)^3), \quad -(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1) \leq \theta_{11} + \gamma \leq 0, \tag{4}$$

where
$$b_{11} = \frac{v_m R_1 \cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)}{3h_{11}^0 (1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11})(1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11} \cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1))}, \quad h_{11}^0 = \delta_1 \frac{\sin(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)}{\sin(\varphi_{11} + \varphi_{21})}.$$

In this section, the strain of the wet material is expressed by the following equality

$$h_{11} = R_1 \cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma) - r_{11} \cos(\theta_{11} + \gamma).$$

Отсюда, с учетом выражений (1) и (2), находим

$$\frac{dh_{11}}{d(\theta_{11} + \gamma)} = \frac{R_1}{1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11}} \sin(\theta_{11} + \gamma) \approx \frac{R_1}{1 + k_{11}} (\theta_{11} + \gamma). \tag{5}$$

According to formulas (3), (4) and (5), we have

$$dG_{11} = -\frac{\rho BR_1 b_{11}}{1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11}} ((\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^3 + (\theta_{11} + \gamma)^3) (\theta_{11} + \gamma) d(\theta_{11} + \gamma). \tag{6}$$

After integrating expression (6), we obtain

$$G_{11} = -\frac{\rho BR_1 b_{11}}{10(1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11})} (2(\theta_{11} + \gamma)^5 + 5(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^3 (\theta_{11} + \gamma)^2) + C_{11}. \tag{7}$$

Constant C_{11} is found by condition $G_{11}(-(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)) = 0$:

$$C_{11} = \frac{\rho BR_1 b_{11}}{10(1 + k_{11}\lambda_{11})} 3(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5.$$

Then we obtain

$$G_{11} = \alpha_{11} (3(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 - 2(\theta_{11} + \gamma)^5 - 5(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^3 (\theta_{11} + \gamma)^2), \tag{8}$$

where

$$-(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1) \leq \theta_{11} + \gamma \leq 0, \quad \alpha_{11} = \frac{\rho v_m BR_1^2 \cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)}{30 h_{11}^0 (1 + k_{11} \lambda_{11})^2 (1 + k_{11} \lambda_{11} \cos(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1))}.$$

Formula (8) determines the patterns of change in the removed fluid that has flowed through the compression zone $A_1 A_3$.

The amount of fluid removed through the compression zones is determined by the

flow rate at the end point A_3 , i.e., moisture content $G_{11}(0)$:

$$G_{11}(0) = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5. \tag{9}$$

In section $A_3 A_4$ of the strain restoration zone, the filtration rate $u_{12\theta}$ is described by the following formula [10]:

$$u_{12\theta} = -b_{12}((\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 - (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^3), \quad 0 \leq \theta_{12} + \gamma \leq \varphi_{14} + \gamma_4 \tag{10}$$

and the strain of the wet material is described by the following expression

$$h_{12} = r_{12} \cos(\theta_{12} + \gamma) - r_{12}(0). \tag{11}$$

Then, according to formula (3), taking into account expressions (10) and (11), we find

$$dG_{12} = \frac{\rho BR_1 b_{12}}{1 + k_{12} \lambda_{12}} ((\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 - (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^3)(\theta_{12} + \gamma) d(\theta_{12} + \gamma). \tag{12}$$

After integration, we get

$$G_{12} = \frac{\rho BR_1 b_{12}}{10(1 + k_{12} \lambda_{12})} (5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^2 - 2(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^5) + C_{12}. \tag{13}$$

According to condition $G_{12}(0) = G_{11}(0) = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5$, we find

$$C_{12} = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5.$$

Then we have

$$G_{12} = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12} (5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^2 - 2(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^5), \tag{14}$$

where

$$0 \leq \theta_{12} + \gamma \leq \varphi_{14} + \gamma_4, \quad \alpha_{12} = \frac{\rho v_m R_1^2 \cos(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)}{30 h_{12}^0 (1 + k_{12} \lambda_{12})^2 (1 + k_{12} \lambda_{12} \cos(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2))}.$$

The amount of fluid removed through the contact surfaces of the compression zone and the first section of the strain restoration zone of the lower roll is determined by the flow rate of fluid through the outlet section of the strain zone, i.e., moisture content $G_{12}(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)$:

$$G_{12}(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4) = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + 3\alpha_{12}(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^5. \quad (15)$$

In section A_4A_2 of the strain restoration zone, the filtration rate $u_{12\theta}$ is described by the following formula [11]:

$$u_{12\theta} = -b_{12}((\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 - (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^3), \quad \varphi_{14} + \gamma_4 \leq \theta_{12} + \gamma \leq \varphi_{12} + \gamma_2. \quad (16)$$

and the strain of the wet material is described by the following expression

$$h_{12} = r_{12} \cos(\theta_{12} + \gamma) - r_{12}(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4). \quad (17)$$

Similar to (12), we have

$$dG_{12} = \frac{\rho BR_1 b_{12}}{1 + k_{12} \lambda_{12}} ((\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 - (\theta_{12} + \gamma)^3) d(\theta_{12} + \gamma)$$

or after integrating and using condition $G_{12}(0) = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5$, we obtain

$$G_{12} = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12}(5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^2 - 2(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^5), \quad (18)$$

where $\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4 \leq \theta_{12} + \gamma \leq \varphi_{12} + \gamma_2$.

Generalizing formulas (14) and (18), we obtain

$$G_{12} = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12}(5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^2 - 2(\theta_{12} + \gamma)^5), \quad (19)$$

where $0 \leq \theta_{12} + \gamma \leq \varphi_{12} + \gamma_2$, $\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4 = \varsigma_1(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)$, $0 < \varsigma_1 \leq 1$.

Thus, the patterns of change in the extracted fluid that has flowed through the contact surfaces of the lower roll are described by formulas (8) and (19).

The amount of fluid removed from the material through the contact surfaces of the

lower roll is determined by its rate at point A_2 , i.e., moisture content $G_{12}(\varphi_{12})$:

$$G_{12}(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2) = 3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12}(5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^5). \quad (20)$$

The patterns of change and the amount of removed fluid that has flowed through the contact surfaces of the upper roll are determined similarly.

They have the following form:

$$G_{21} = \alpha_{21} (3(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^5 - 2(\theta_{21} - \gamma)^5 - 5(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^3 (\theta_{11} - \gamma)^2), \quad (21)$$

where

$$-(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1) \leq \theta_{21} - \gamma \leq 0, \quad \alpha_{21} = \frac{\rho v_m B R_2^2 \cos(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)}{30 h_{21}^0 (1 + k_{21} \lambda_{21})^2 (1 + k_{21} \lambda_{21} \cos(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1))};$$

$$G_{22} = 3\alpha_{21} (\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{22} (5(\varphi_{24} - \gamma_4)^3 (\theta_{22} - \gamma)^2 - 2(\theta_{22} - \gamma)^5), \quad (22)$$

where

$$0 \leq \theta_{22} - \gamma \leq \varphi_{22} - \gamma_2, \quad \varphi_{14} - \gamma_4 = \zeta_2 (\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2), \quad 0 < \zeta_2 \leq 1;$$

$$\alpha_{22} = \frac{v_m \rho R_2^2 \cos(\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)}{30 h_{22}^0 (1 + k_{22} \lambda_{22})^2 (1 + k_{22} \lambda_{22} \cos(\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2))}.$$

$$G_{22} (\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2) = 3\alpha_{21} (\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{22} (5(\varphi_{24} - \gamma_4)^3 (\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)^5). \quad (23)$$

The amount of fluid removed from the processed material during the pressing process is equal to the sum of the amount of fluid removed through the contact curves of the lower and upper rolls:

$$G_{y\partial} = 3\alpha_{11} (\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12} (5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3 (\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^5) +$$

$$+ 3\alpha_{21} (\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{22} (5(\varphi_{24} - \gamma_4)^3 (\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)^5). \quad (24)$$

With known amount of fluid removed, the amount of fluid extracted from the wet material during the squeezing process is determined by the following expression [11]:

$$W_{y\partial} = \frac{G_{y\partial}}{\rho B v_m} 100 \%, \quad (25)$$

where v_m – is the feed rate of the material.

During roll pressing, the following equalities hold [11]:

$$W_{ocm} = W_{нач} - W_{y\partial},$$

where W_{ocm} , $W_{нач}$ – are the residual and initial moisture content of the pressed material, respectively.

From (24) and (25), it follows that the residual moisture content of the roll squeezing of fibrous materials is determined by the following expression:

$$W_{ocm} = W_{naq} - \frac{1}{\rho B v_b} (3\alpha_{11}(\varphi_{11} + \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{12}(5(\varphi_{14} + \gamma_4)^3(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{12} + \gamma_2)^5) + 3\alpha_{21}(\varphi_{21} - \gamma_1)^5 + \alpha_{22}(5(\varphi_{24} - \gamma_4)^3(\varphi_{24} - \gamma_2)^2 - 2(\varphi_{22} - \gamma_2)^5)) . \quad (26)$$

Thus, the analytical dependence (26) was determined, which describes the residual moisture content of the pressed material.

Results

Mathematical models were developed for the patterns of changes in the removed fluid in the contact zone and the residual moisture content of the wet material during the roll pressing.

Conclusions

1. From the analysis of the calculated data and graphs (Fig. 2), it follows:

– the amount of fluid removed at the beginning of the compression zone grows faster, which is associated with a rapid increase in the compression strain of the wet material. Then the growth rate of the removed fluid becomes less, and at the end of the compression zone, the removed fluid is stabilized, which is associated with a decrease in the compression strain of the wet material.

– the patterns of change in the removed fluid in the strain restoration zone depend on number $\zeta_i = \sqrt[3]{0,4} = 0,74$, which determines the position of the point where the fluid changes its direction. At $0 < \zeta_i < 0,74$, the fluid extracted under pressing is less than at the end of the compression zone. At that, fluid is reabsorbed into the wet material from the roll cover. At $0,74 \leq \zeta_i < 1$, the amount of fluid removed after pressing is greater than at the end of the compression zone. At the beginning of the strain restoration zone, the fluid moves from the coating to the wet material, and at the end of this zone, moisture is reabsorbed from the roll coating, and the amount of fluid removed from the wet material in the strain restoration zone is greater than the absorbed amount. At $\zeta_i = 0,74$, the amount of moisture removed during pressing is equal to the amount of moisture removed at the end of the compression zone,

that is, the amount of fluid removed and absorbed in the strain restoration zone is the same.

Fig. 2. Graphs of the change in the removed fluid flowing through the contact curve of the lower roll -

$$1 - \varphi_{14} = \frac{1}{4} \varphi_{12}; \quad 2 - \varphi_{14} = \frac{1}{2} \varphi_{12}; \quad 3 - \varphi_{14} = \frac{3}{4} \varphi_{12}, \quad 4 - \varphi_{14} = \varphi_{12}.$$

2. The residual moisture content of the fibrous material also depends on ζ_i . At $0 < \zeta_i < 0,74$, the residual moisture is greater than the moisture at the end of the compression zone, due to the reverse flow of fluid from the coating into the wet material. At $0,74 \leq \zeta_i < 1$, the residual moisture is less than the moisture at the end of the compression zone, due to the removal of fluid in the strain restoration zone. At $\zeta_i = 1$, the residual moisture is the least.

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